

DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF THERMOPLASTICS/GRAPHITE FIBER COMPOSITES

M. Kitanaka, H. Kobayashi, T. Norita, Y. Kawatsu
Pioneering R & D Lab.
Toray Ind., Inc.
2-1, 3-Chome, Sonoyama, Otsu, Shiga, 520 Japan

Summary

Compressive strength and damage after impact in several thermoplastics (Nylon 6, PEEK, PES, PPS and AS) and graphite fiber composites are evaluated and compared with those of epoxy matrix system.

Nylon 6, PEEK and PES matrix laminates show excellent damage tolerance.

The damage area caused by the impact is determined by ILSS and G_{1c} . The lower the ILSS or G_{1c} , the larger the damage area.

The residual compressive strength after impact is determined by the damage area but does not depend on the resistance of crack propagation under compressive load.

Introduction

As matrices for graphite fiber reinforced composites, thermoplastic resins have been recognized to offer some potential advantages over thermosetting resin. (1,2,3) These advantages include short molding cycle time, infinite shelf life of prepreg, capability of fusion bonding, recycling and reparability, and excellent impact resistance. Especially damage tolerance of thermoplastic resins has received considerable attention in recent years.

Damage tolerance of graphite fiber reinforced polyether-etherketone(4) and K-polymer (5) has been well demonstrated.

In this paper, the compressive strength and the damage after impact in several thermoplastics and graphite fiber composites, and comparison with those of epoxy matrix system are presented. We also discuss the correlation between the damage tolerance of the laminates and the properties of neat resins, and the mechanism of decrease of compressive strength by impact.

Experimental

Matrix Resins and Graphite Fiber

The resins evaluated in this study are summerized in Table I. For comparison 350°F cure epoxy resin named #3620 was studied additionally. Tensile properties of neat resins were evaluated using compression molded sheets which were prepared under the condition simulating the cooling rate for laminate sheets fabrication.

Graphite fiber was "Torayca" T-300 in the form of woven fabric #6343 (plain weave). T-300 fabric was heat treated at 380°C for 2 hours to remove the sizing agent before laminating with thermoplastic resin. After this heat treatment no surface sizing was employed, and so the interfacial properties for each matrix resin were not optimized.

Preparation of Laminates

The laminates were prepared by film stacking method, namely thermoplastic resin sheet or powder and graphite fabric were stacked alternately then consolidated to a laminate by heat and pressure. The conditions for preparing the laminates are summerized in Table II.

Graphite fabrics were lay-upped to form quasi-isotropic laminate : $[(\pm 45, 0/90, 0/90)_2 / (\pm 45, 0/90)_3 / \pm 45]_s$

The dimensions of the laminates were roughly 5 mmx330 mmx330 mm and two sheets were prepared for each matrix resin.

In the case when matrix resin was PPS acoustic emission was detected after removing the laminate from the mold. From microscopic inspection of the cross-section of the laminate many micro crackings were clearly observed. This acoustic emission is considered to be caused by thermal cracking which was generated by thermal stress on cooling process.

Preparation of Test Specimens

Test specimens for compression, compression after impact, and interlaminar shear strength were cut from the laminates. The dimensional accuracy of compression test specimen was controlled within 1/1000 in. The dimension of the specimen is shown in Fig. 1.

Table I Matrix Resins and Their Properties

Resin	Type	Supplier	Crystallinity	Transition Temperature		Tensile	
				Tg (°C)	Tm (°C)	Modulus (GPa)	Elongation (%)
Nylon 6	CM1010	Toray	Crys.	50	225	2.7	80
PPS	— ^{a)}	Phillips	Crys.	90	280	2.9	5
PEEK	15P	ICI	Crys.	143	334	4.6	25
PEEK	45P	ICI	Crys.	143	334	4.5	30
AS ^{b)}	1100	Toray	Amr.	103	—	4.3	4
PES	200P	ICI	Amr.	225	—	3.1	20
EPOXY	#3620	Toray	(Amr.)	210	—	3.4	4

a) linear high molecular weight polymer for film and fiber forming.

b) poly (acrylonitrile/styrene) copolymer.

Table II Molding Conditions for Preparing Laminate Sheets

Resin	Heating			Cooling		
	Temp (°C)	Pressure (MPa)	Time (min)	Pressure (MPa)	Cooling Rate (°C/min)	Removing Temp. from mold (°C)
N6	280	4.9	10	5.9	10~15	100
PPS	330	4.9	10	5.9	10~15	150
PEEK	380	8.8	30	8.8	10~15	150
AS	250	4.9	10	5.9	10~15	60
PES	380	8.8	30	8.8	10~15	150
EPOXY #3620	180	0.6	120	0.6	2.0	50

Fig. 1 Dimension of test specimen (unit: mm)

Impact Test

Impact energy was applied to the laminates by a apparatus illustrated in Fig. 2 which was similar to the method reported by Byers(6). The steel tip with a hemispherical nose of 5/8 inch (15.7mm), which was placed on the laminate vertically, was impacted by a falling weight. The capacity of falling weight was 12 lb (5.45Kg). Energy levels were 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, 2500, 3000 in-lb/in (22.2~133.5 J/cm). For each energy level,

Fig. 2 Arrangement for applying impact energy

the height of the falling weight was adjusted according to the thickness of the laminate.

In addition, as an extreme case of impact damage, through-penetration impact test was performed for AS, PES, PEEK (15P) and epoxy matrix laminates. The laminates were supported under the same condition as Fig. 2 and impacted by a dart with the same hemispherical nose as above by using Dynatup Model 8000 drop weight impact tester.

The maximum load and the energy to the maximum load were measured by Model ETI 300 data processor.

Observation of Impact Damage

Polished cross-section of the impacted area of the test specimen was inspected by microscope. The impacted area was also examined by ultrasonic C-scan.

The depth of the indentation on the impacted surface, which is an important index for representing a barely visible impact damage (BVID), was also measured by dial gauge.

Compression Test

Compressive properties of test specimens which were impacted as previously described were evaluated with the apparatus shown in Fig. 3 (6). Compressive strain (ϵ) was measured at four points of the specimen and average value was calculated. Compressive strength (σ) was calculated from equation

$$\sigma = P/W t \quad (1)$$

where P is the compression load at failure, W is the width and

Fig. 3 Fixture for compression test

Fig. 4 ILSS test method (Unit: mm)

t is the thickness of the specimen respectively.

Compression test on the through-penetrated specimen was performed in the same way as mentioned above.

Short Beam Shear Strength

Test method for measuring apparent interlaminar shear strength (τ) is shown in Fig. 4. Interlaminar shear strength was calculated from equation

$$\tau = 3P/2Wt \quad (2)$$

where P is the load at failure, W is the width and t is the thickness of the specimen respectively.

Model Composite Specimen with artificial defect

To examine the mechanism of decrease of compressive strength by impact, epoxy matrix model composite specimen was prepared in which delamination was introduced intentionally at the center of compression test specimen by inserting "Teflon" film between the layer of the laminate. The diameter and the number of "Teflon" film was varied in the range of 0.5~2 inch and 3~11 ply respectively. The films were placed at same intervals with respect to the thickness of the laminate.

Result and Discussion

Damage by Impact

Cross-sections of damaged part were inspected by microscope and the micrographs for the case of the energy level 1500 in-lb/in (66.7 J/cm) are shown in Fig. 5. For each resin system, damage by impact can be classified into three types as previously reported (8), fiber breakage, intra-ply cracking and delamination.

In the case when matrix resin is AS, PPS and epoxy, extreme delamination and intra-ply cracking are observed. On the other hand, in PEEK and PES matrix systems, the delamination and the intra-ply cracking are smaller and localized in limited area.

The depth of the indentation at the impacted point versus impact energy are plotted in Fig. 6 for each resin system. From the viewpoint of barely visible impact damage (BVID), the residual compressive strength versus the depth of the indentation are plotted in Fig. 7. From Fig. 7, it can be seen that PEEK and PES matrix system show much deeper indentation than AS and PPS matrix system if compared at the same residual compressive strength. This means that the damage can be easily detected by the visual inspection of the appearance when matrix resin is PEEK or PES.

The damages of the laminates after impact observed by ultrasonic C-scans are shown in Table III. The image detected by ultrasonic C-scans represents the maximum area of delamination. It can be seen from Table III that the higher the impact energy, the large the delamination area.

Fig. 8 shows the dependence of the damage area on the impact energy for each matrix resin. AS, PPS and epoxy have larger damage area compared to N6, PEEK and PES.

At the moment of impact, three types of stresses should be generated; shear stress, bending stress and contact stress (9). It is reasonable to think that the delaminations in composite initiate when shear stress generated by the impact exceeds the shear strength of the material, and then propagate to a certain size depending on its interlaminar fracture toughness. Energy balance at the impact can be approximately expressed

$$E - E_o = E_f + nG_{1c}A \quad (3)$$

where E ; impact energy, E_f ; energy consumed for fiber breakage, E_o ; energy for initiation of delamination, G_{1c} ; interlaminar fracture toughness, A ; damage area, n ; number of delaminations.

This aspect of the delamination can be represented schematically in Fig. 9. So it can be said that the damage area is smaller when the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and the interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{1c}) are higher in the

(a) EPOXY #3620

(d) PES

(b) AS

(e) PEEK (15P)

(c) PPS

(f) PEEK (45P)

Fig. 5 Cross-Section of impacted part.
The data of epoxy #3620 is cited from reference (7)

Fig. 6 Depth of indentation by impact

Fig. 7 Relationship between residual compressive strength and depth of indentation

Table III Damage area after impact

RESIN	Impact Energy (lb-in /in)					
	500	1,000	1,500	2,000	2,500	3,000
AS	 1.62					
PPS	 2.74					
PES	 1.71					
PEEK (15P)	 1.83					
PEEK (45P)	 1.78					
Nylon 6	 0.70					

a) damage area (in²)

Fig. 8 Dependence of damage area on impact energy

Fig. 9 Schematic representation of the effect of ILSS and G_{1c} on damage area by impact

case when E_f is the same order.

It is important to be noticed that the damage area is also related with fiber strength. From equation (3), the smaller the energy consumption for fiber breakage, the larger the delamination. For example, the composite reinforced by high strength fiber will give larger delamination because less energy is consumed for fiber breakage. It should also be noticed that there exist the lowest limit of damage area which is determined by interlaminar shear strength of material regardless of G_{1c} as shown in Fig. 9.

In Table IV ILSS, G_{1c} and elongation at break (ϵ) for each matrix resin are summarized. The data of G_{1c} is not evaluated in this study and is not sufficiently available, then we will discuss the elongation at break (ϵ) instead of G_{1c} because G_{1c} can be roughly approximated to ϵ of matrix resin from following consideration. At the crack propagation front, matrix resin can be considered to be drawn and teared. So the energy which is necessary to propagate the crack should correspond to the energy which is consumed up to tensile break. As Young's modulus of each matrix resin is similar order, the energy which is consumed at tensile break can be replaced by elongation at break for rough approximation.

From Table IV and Fig. 8, it can be seen that in the case when ILSS or ϵ is low, the damage area is quite large.

Table IV ILSS, ϵ , G_{1c} for each matrix resin

Resin	ILSS (MPa)	ϵ (%)	G_{1c} ^{a)} (KJ/m)
Nylon 6	49	80	>0.88
PES	58	20	
PEEK(15P)	64	25	1.4, 2.1
PEEK(45P)	72	30	1.4, 2.1
AS	43	4	
PPS	28	5	1.3
EPOXY #3620	59	4	0.30

a) data of PEEK and PPS are cited from reference (4), (10), (11)

Compressive Properties after Impact

Dependence of compressive strength after impact on impact energy is shown in Fig. 10. In Fig. 10, dotted line shows the strength of Al alloy (7075-T6) evaluated in the same manner and normalized by density. As a whole residual compressive strength decreases when impact energy increases but the dependence of residual compressive strength on impact energy is quite different for each matrix resin.

In the case when AS, PPS and epoxy resins are matrices the residual compressive strength decreases markedly even when impact energy is 500 in-lb/in. On the other hand Nylon 6, PEEK and PES matrix composites show excellent damage tolerance.

The dependence of the compressive strength on the damage

Fig. 10 Dependence of residual compressive strength on impact energy

area evaluated by ultrasonic C-scans is shown in Fig. 11. As the compressive strength of the laminate sheet before impact is quite different depending on its matrix resin, the residual compressive strength ratio is plotted in Fig. 11. The residual compressive strength ratio is defined by σ/σ_0 where σ and σ_0 are the compressive strength after and before impact respectively.

From Fig. 11 it can be seen that the residual compressive strength ratio depends qualitatively on the damage area in a similar manner regardless of its matrix resin.

Fig. 12 shows the dependence of residual compressive strength ratio on model defect diameter. From comparison of Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, the dependence of residual compressive strength on the impact damage is quite similar to that of the model composite sample which has artificial delamination of 5 ply. This indicates that compressive strength after impact is determined by the area of damage caused by the impact, not by the fracture toughness to prevent the propagation of the delamination under compressive load, which is the contrary to the aspect as previously reported (4).

Compressive strength after penetration impact

The maximum load and the energy at through-penetration impact test are summarized in Table V compared with Al alloy (7075-T6). Typical patterns of P- δ curves are shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 11 Dependence of residual strength ratio on damage diameter

Fig. 12 Dependence of residual strength ratio on model defect diameter

Fig. 13 Load-deflection curve at through-penetration impact test

The maximum load are not different for each material except for Al alloy. However as shown in Fig. 13, the $P-\delta$ curves are quite different for tough resin system such as PEEK and brittle system such as AS. Namely, the former shows yielding behavior similar to Al alloy but the latter does no significant yielding on the $P-\delta$ curve.

The compressive strength of the penetrated through specimen is also summarized in Table V. PEEK resin system shows improved compressive strength when compared with other resin systems. However in comparison with Al alloy, even if the strength is normalized by the density, the compressive strength of PEEK resin system is lower than that of Al alloy. From this aspect, it seems necessary to study extensively the compressive properties of the laminate with open hole hereafter.

Table V Test result of through-penetration impact

Properties	AS	PES	PEEK(15)	Epoxy	Al-alloy
Thickness (mm)	5.31	5.03	5.05	4.64	4.95
Pmax (Kg)	940	949	962	676	2380 (1322) ^{a)}
Em (J)	19.1	33.9	45.4	16.7	168 (93.6) ^{a)}
Residual Compressive Strength (MPa)	155	171	195	169	386 (221) ^{a)}

a) relative value normalized by density.

Conclusion

Compressive strength and damage after impact in several thermoplastics and graphite fiber composites were evaluated, and compared with those of epoxy matrix composite.

1. N6, PEEK and PES matrix composites show excellent damage tolerance.
2. Damage area is determined by ILSS and G_{1c} . The lower the ILSS or G_{1c} , the larger the damage area.
3. Compressive strength after impact is determined by the damage area caused by the impact, but does not depend on the interlaminar fracture toughness which prevents the crack to propagate under compressive load.

References

1. J.T. Hoggatt, "Study of Graphite Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites" Naval Air Systems Command Report No. D180-18034-1, February 1974.
2. J.H. Laakso and J.T. Hoggatt, "Development of a Low-Cost Graphite Reinforced Composite Primary Structural Component" Naval Air Development Center Final Report, Contract N62269-74-C-0368, December 1976.
3. D.J. Willats, "Advances in The Use of High Performance Continuous Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics" SAMPE Journal, 6, September/October 1984.
4. D.R. Carlile and D.C. Leach, "Damage and Notch Sensitivity of Graphite/PEEK Composite" 15th National SAMPE Technical Conference, 82, October 4-6, 1983.

5. H.H. Gibbs, "K-Polymer : A New Experimental Thermoplastic Matrix Resin for Advanced Structural Aerospace Composites" 29th National SAMPE Symposium, 1073, April 3-5, 1984.
6. B.A. Byers, "Behavior of Damaged Graphite/Epoxy Laminates Under Compression Loading" NASA Contractor Report No. 159293, August 1980.
7. A. Nishimura, N. Veda, and H.S. Matsuda, "Now Fabric Structures of Carbon Fiber" 28th National SAMPE Symposium, 71, April 12-14, 1984.
8. M.D. Rhodes, J.G. Williams, and J.H. Starnes, JR., "Low-Velocity Impact Damage in Graphite-Fiber Reinforced Epoxy Laminates" 34th Annual Technical Conference, Reinforced Plastics/Composite Institute The Society of the Plastic Industry, Inc., Section 20-D, 1979.
9. A.L. Dobyns and T.R. Porter, "A Study of Structural Integrity of Graperite Composite Structure Subjected to Low Velocity Impact" 35th Annual Technical Conference, Reinforced Plastics/Composite Institute The Society of the Plastic Industry, Inc., Section 17-B, 1980.
10. J.T. Hartness, "Polyether etherketone Matrix Composites" 14th National SAMPE Technical Conference, 26, October 12-14, 1982.
11. C.C. Martin Ma, J.E. O'Connor, and Alex Y. Lou, "Polyphenylene Sulfide High Performance Composites" 29th National SAMPE Symposium, 753, April 3-5, 1984.

